

Studies with Polystyrene Supported Aluminium Ferrocyanide Membranes

W. U. MALIK*, D. K. RASTOGI** and SAT PAUL ARORA

Chemical Laboratories, Mukand Lal National College, Yamuna Nagar-135 001 (Ambala)-India

Manuscript received 12 October 1979, accepted 19 May 1980

Permeability and potential measurements with various electrolytes KCl, KBr, KNO_3 , KCNS, K_2SO_4 , NaCl, LiCl, CaCl₂, BaCl₂ and MgCl₂ on polystyrene supported aluminium ferrocyanide membrane have been carried out. The results show that the order of permeability for anions is $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and the order for cations is $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ (1 : 1 electrolytes); $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$ (2 : 1 electrolytes). Measurement of potential shows an initial increase after which it attains a constant value. The order of membrane potential values for the said anions and cations is reverse of the order of permeability thus indicating the greater the membrane potential, lower the permeability and vice versa. Dynamic response time, fixed charge density and effect of binder percentage on potential have also been reported.

THE literature survey reveals that extensive studies on the membrane behaviour of natural and artificial polymeric membranes¹⁻³ have been carried out, but the information regarding the relation between the exchange properties and behaviour of synthetic membranes is meagre. Recently Malik and co-workers⁴⁻⁸ have investigated the measurement of potential and permeability of the membranes prepared from inorganic gels. However, lesser attention has been paid to determine the correlation between ion exchange properties and membrane behaviour of polystyrene supported membranes.

The present communication deals with the measurement of permeability, membrane potential, dynamic response time, fixed charge density and effect of binder percentage of aluminium ferrocyanide membranes.

Experimental

Preparation of the Membranes : Aluminium ferrocyanide gel was prepared by mixing 0.02M potassium ferrocyanide (A.R.) solution with 0.04M aluminium chloride (A.R.) solution. It was thoroughly washed with double distilled water, filtered, dried and finally sieved into 200 mesh size powder.

Polystyrene supported membranes of aluminium ferrocyanide were prepared⁹ by mixing aluminium ferrocyanide gel and polystyrene (50 mesh size powder) in different proportions by weight. The mixture was homogenised in a mortar and 1.5 gm of this mass was put in a die of 2.5 cm diameter. The die was then kept in a specimen mount press

and heated gradually upto a temperature of 110° under pressure (6500 to 7000 psi). A large number of membranes containing 15, 20, 25 and 30% of polystyrene were prepared by this method.

Permeability measurements : Permeability measurements were carried out using the Hartung and Willis¹⁰ constant flow method. The membrane under investigation was fitted between two flanges of permeability cell and measurements were carried out by using different electrolytes in the upper half cell. The hydrostatic pressure on each side of the membrane was always kept equal by adjusting the rate of flow of solution and conductivity water across the membrane. The rate of flow of the effluent was kept constant (100 ± 1 ml) per hour. The analysis of the effluent coming out of the lower half cell was made conductometrically. Knowing the rate of flow and concentration of the effluent (coming out of lower half cell), the permeability in millimoles per hour was determined.

Potential measurements : Membranes in their various cationic forms were obtained by dipping them in 1-2M solutions of a particular electrolyte for about 48 hours to ensure complete exchange. The membranes were dried completely and cemented to one end of a pyrex glass tube. The tube was inserted in a corked beaker. Solutions of different concentrations of electrolyte were filled in the tube and in the beaker. The membrane potentials were determined indirectly using cells of the type described by Michaelis¹¹.

SCE : Solution (C_1) : Membrane : Solution (C_2) : SCE
where $C_1 = 10.C_2$.

* Professor and Head, Chemistry Department, U.O.R., Roorkee (India).

** Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut (India).

The variation in potential with time was recorded, until potential was maximum. All measurements were made at $(25 \pm 1^\circ)$ in a thermostat.

Results and Discussion

The permeability of aluminium ferrocyanide membrane for different electrolytes (Table 1) show

TABLE 1—PERMEABILITY OF DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES ACROSS ALUMINIUM FERROCYANIDE MEMBRANE HAVING 15% BINDER (ELECTROLYTE CONCENTRATION 0.05M)

Electrolytes with common cation	Permeability (milli-moles/hour)	Electrolytes with common anion	Permeability (milli-moles/hour)
KCl	0.5070	KCl	0.5070
KBr	0.0624	NaCl	0.1480
KNO ₃	0.0532	LiCl	0.1260
KCNS	0.0417	BaCl ₂	0.0822
K ₂ SO ₄	0.0382	CaCl ₂	0.0575
—	—	MgCl ₂	0.0455

that the order of diffusion for anions is $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and for cations $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ (1:1 electrolytes) and $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$ (2:1 electrolytes). It is also clear from permeability data that the rate of permeation of cations is more than anions. This confirms that the membrane is negatively charged and therefore, allows cations more easily to pass through it while anions are not easily passed due to repulsive forces.

The various factors which control electrolyte permeability through a membrane are charge on the membrane, its porosity, the charge and size of the diffusing ion, adsorption, exchange capacity of membrane material and position of the ion in the Hofmeister series.

The fixed charges on the membrane act in two ways. Firstly, these exclude co-ions from the membrane phase due to electrostatic repulsion and secondly increase the mobility of counter ions towards it. The transference of ions through the membrane is also influenced by the size of the hydrated ions. Completely hydrated ions would be less exchangeable than the partially hydrated ones and would consequently show smaller diffusion through the pores of the membrane.

The permeability order for anions $\text{Cl}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{CNS}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ is same as their position in the lyotropic series. But the behaviour of SO_4^{2-} ion is altogether different. In this case, the permeability value is very low inspite of the fact that a large electrical driving force should operate due to the two negative charges on the ion. It appears that a very large hydration shell envelopes the ion (evident from the position in the lyotropic series) resulting in the reduction of the electrostatic driving force

which will subsequently retard diffusion. It is evident from the data that the sequence for anions is also according to their size. The ions of the smaller size (Cl^- and Br^-) pass through the membrane more easily than bigger ones (NO_3^- , CNS^- and SO_4^{2-}).

The order of diffusion for cations ($\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ and $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$) is opposite to that of their hydrated ionic size. Li^+ (much hydrated) possesses lower permeability values than sodium and potassium (less hydrated). Similarly, Mg^{2+} (much hydrated) possesses lesser permeability than Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} (less hydrated). The diffusion rate for cations is also in accordance with the position of the ion in the Hofmeister series.

According to Eisenmann's model^{1,2}, the selectivity depends upon the energies of hydration and ion site interaction. The diffusion rates in our case viz. $\text{K}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ and $\text{Ba}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+}$ point towards a weak field strength, i.e., normal sequence is followed in case of membranes under investigation.

The potential values (Table 2) due to diffusion of electrolytes through the membrane show that the values for anions are high and for cations are low. This is in good agreement with the fact that higher the potential lower the permeability. The order of potential values for anions is $\text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{CNS}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$ and for cations is $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+$ (1:1 electrolytes); $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+}$ (2:1 electrolytes).

TABLE 2—POTENTIALS OF DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES OF ALUMINIUM FERROCYANIDE MEMBRANE HAVING 15% BINDER (ELECTROLYTE CONCENTRATION, INSIDE SOLUTION CONCENTRATION/OUTSIDE SOLUTION CONCENTRATION=0.1/0.01M)

Electrolytes with common cation	Potentials (mV)	Electrolytes with common anion	Potentials (mV)
KCl	31.4	KCl	31.4
KBr	32.5	NaCl	33.9
KNO ₃	33.4	LiCl	49.0
KCNS	33.8	BaCl ₂	18.5
K ₂ SO ₄	35.4	CaCl ₂	19.8
—	—	MgCl ₂	20.1

The method developed by Altug and Hair^{1,3} based on TMS theory was employed to determine the fixed charge density ($w\bar{X}$) of the membrane material where \bar{X} represents the number of ionised sites per unit volume and $w = \pm 1$ depending on the nature of dissociation sites. These E_{TOT} values were plotted against the log of external solution concentration (Fig. 1). The experimental values of membrane potential were also plotted against log concentration of external solution in the same diagram. The theoretical value which coincides with experimental one, gives the value of fixed charge density of the membrane. The fixed charge density of aluminium ferrocyanide is $-0.15N$ at concentration ratio 1.0/0.1M, $-0.04N$ at concentration

Fig. 1. Membrane potential for different values of fixed charge density.

ratio 0.1/0.01M and $-0.02N$ at concentration ratio 0.05/0.005M. These studies show that fixed charged density is not a constant quantity but depends upon the concentration of the solution separating the membrane.

The dynamic response time of membrane electrode was determined by recording the resulting potential versus time (Fig. 2) for different concentrations of electrolyte (keeping $C_1 = 10.C_2$). The highest peak of the curve gives the equilibration time which is about 500 seconds for this membrane. This equilibration time is almost negligible as compared to other ion-selective electrodes and is probably due to its semi-crystalline nature.

Fig. 2. Dynamic response time of membrane electrode.

The effect of concentration of binder on the membrane behaviour was investigated in the range 15 to 30% (Table 3). The effect of concentration of

TABLE 3—POTENTIALS OF ALUMINIUM FERROCYANIDE MEMBRANES HAVING VARYING AMOUNTS OF BINDER (ELECTROLYTE CONCENTRATION=0.1/0.01M)

Electrolytes	Obs rved potentials (mV) in the membranes having			
	15% binder	20% binder	25% binder	30% binder
LiCl	49.0	49.1	49.1	49.2
NaCl	33.9	33.8	33.9	34.0
KCl	31.4	31.5	31.4	31.6
KBr	32.5	32.7	32.6	32.6
KNO ₃	33.4	33.4	33.5	33.5
KONS	33.8	33.7	33.8	33.7
K ₂ SO ₄	35.4	35.5	35.6	35.6
MgCl ₂	20.1	20.1	20.0	20.1
CaCl ₂	19.8	19.9	20.0	19.8
BaCl ₂	18.5	18.5	18.6	18.5

binder on membrane behaviour was not investigated in the membranes having less than 15% polystyrene owing to their instability and more than 30% polystyrene owing to separation of exchange particles by the binder. It was, therefore, concluded that the π -electrons of the binder do not affect the electrochemical behaviour of the exchanger at least in these concentration ranges. However, possibility of this factor influencing the membrane behaviour in dilute solutions cannot be completely ignored.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Principal T. R. Chadha, M. L. N. College, Yamuna Nagar for providing facilities and to U. G. C. (India) for the award of financial assistance to one of them (S.P.A.).

References

1. T. THEORELL, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1956, **21**, 9.
2. H. J. ZWOLINSKY, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1949, **53**, 1426.
3. A. J. MEACKIE and P. MEARS, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1955, **A-232**, 498.
4. W. U. MALIK and F. A. SIDDIQI, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1963, **18**, 161.
5. W. U. MALIK and S. A. ANWAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 491.
6. W. U. MALIK and H. ARIF, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1967, **40**, 1746.
7. W. U. MALIK, S. K. SRIVASTAVA, V. M. BHANDARI and SATISH KUMAR, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1974, **47**, 1.
8. W. U. MALIK, S. K. SRIVASTAVA, R. K. GULATI and SAR PAUL ARORA, *J. Electrochem. Soc. India*, 1977, **26**, 3.
9. M. R. J. WYLLIE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1950, **54**, 204.
10. G. M. WILLIS, A. T. AUSTIN and E. J. HARTUNG, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1944, **40**, 520.
11. MICHAELIS, *Kolloid-Z.*, 1963, **62**, 1.
12. G. EISENMANN, *Biophys. J. Suppl.*, 1962, **2**, 259.
13. J. ALTUG and M. L. HAIR, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 599.